

Non-native Finnish speaker?

Participate in a spoken interaction study!

Aasis research project – developing automatic assessment of spoken interaction

University of Jyväskylä, University of Helsinki, Aalto University
Research Council of Finland (2023-2027)

Who?

If you speak Finnish as a second or foreign language, welcome!

Why participate?

- All kinds of speakers are needed
- We are interested in your opinion
- Support development of an online tool
- Contribute to science

How do I participate?

Data collection: A-building (A012) in
Seminaarinmäki

Duration: 1 h

Contact: maria.e.e.kautonen@jyu.fi
and we'll set up a time for you!

You can also participate
with a friend!

For more information

bit.ly/aasisinfo

A big
thank you
for your time